

Biogas from wood-based residues at waste management centres

Biogas is derived from a multitude of organic waste materials from public and private waste management centres in Northern Europe. Wood bark from industry, urban wood residues, household waste, some construction-, demolition- and packaging wastes, also low-value forest residues are processed after sorting and mixed with other organic materials by anaerobic digestion (fermentation). The resulting bio-fuels (as liquids) are used in vehicles, district heating networks and local electricity consumption, as well as process gas in miscellaneous industrial processes. Fermented waste materials from old landfills are used in the biogas process as well. The fermented and fresh forest industry waste can be transformed into fertilizers and other value-added products.

Regional coverage and transferability

The basic raw materials for biogas can be found everywhere across Europe and some wood-based wastes can be mixed with other organic wastes. Technology is available for different scales of production.

The market potential of biogas products is positive both for legislative reasons (fuels for land vehicle and ships, peat restrictions) and for the increasing industrial demands and opportunities across sectors and regions. Fermentation waste materials, upgrading environmental efficiency and improving the carbon footprints make biogas attractive for waste management centres.

Exploitation within and across Europe is given, but should be accompanied by market feasibility studies at local and national levels. Development of distribution networks and further improvement in material efficiency and testing for local or specific wood materials (lignin-rich materials) can accelerate implementation.

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Innovative, safe, environmental friendly and closed-loop production technology that can be applied in various scales of production and in different industrial environments
- ▶ Contributes to substitution of fossil fuels and peat
- ▶ Raising public acceptance of wood waste management for value-added products
- ▶ Improving restoration of old landfills and providing solutions to avoid landfilling